

THERMAL DAMAGE EVALUATION OF CFRP PROCESSED WITH NANOSECOND UV LASER PULSES

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Keywords: CFRP, Laser machining, Raman spectroscopy

ABSTRACT

We aim to develop a high quality laser processing technology for CFRPs using a pulsed laser at a wavelength of 258nm. We previously reported high aspect ratio (>80) laser cutting with no heat-affected zone (HAZ) and high-speed laser piercing for 1.6mm thick CFRPs using nanosecond 258nm laser pulses [1-2]. These results indicate that 258nm laser processing is non-thermal in nature and therefore the temperature rise of the cutting surface is suppressed. In order to study the wavelength dependence of thermal damage for CFRP laser processing, Raman spectroscopy was performed on the resin around the processed groove, laser-cut at wavelengths of 258nm, 515nm, and 1030nm.

The samples were T800S/3900-2B unidirectional laminate with a thickness of 1.6mm. The duration, repetition rate and average power of the 258nm laser pulses were 7ns, 10kHz and 1W respectively. The Raman spectra corresponding to the ether bond (C-O-C) and the carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) disappeared near the laser-cut grooves, which indicates chemical alteration of the resin by laser irradiation. The Raman intensity of these peaks was studied as a function of the distance perpendicular to the surface of the laser-cut groove, and it was observed that the resin is less damaged for the laser wavelength of 258nm compared to 515nm and 1030nm.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) are finding many new applications in various fields, including the aviation and automobile industries, primarily because CFRPs are lightweight, strong, and durable. Currently, machining and water jets are normally used for CFRP cutting, but there are problems with machining accuracy and costs. Recently, laser processing has been researched as an alternative technology for cutting CFRP [3-5], but the HAZ, which is thermal damage from laser irradiation, is a major obstacle to using laser cutting as a standard process. In this study, we show the feasibility of high quality laser processing technology for CFRPs, using a pulsed laser at a wavelength of 258nm. We previously reported high aspect ratio (>80) laser cutting with no HAZ and high-speed laser piercing for 1.6mm thick CFRPs using nanosecond 258nm laser pulses [1-2]. CFRPs were processed at wavelengths of 258nm, 515nm and 1030nm, and the Raman spectra of the ether bond (C-O-C) and carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) was studied as a function of distance perpendicular to the surface of the laser-cut groove, to determine the existence and range of damage.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Samples

The samples were T800S/3900-2B unidirectional laminate (supplied by Toray Industries, Inc.), with a thickness of 1.6mm. The sample's lay-up was $[0]_8$.

2.2 Laser machining

The pulse duration, repetition rate and average power of the 258nm laser pulses were 7ns, 10kHz and 1W respectively. The linearly-polarized laser pulses were focused to 20 μ m in diameter on the surface of CFRPs. The CFRP was moved once (single scan) at a speed of 0.05 to 1mm/s orthogonal to the orientation of the carbon fibers.

2.3 Raman spectroscopy

In order to observe the damage of the resin as a function of the distance from the laser-cut grooves, CFRPs were cut by a diamond saw perpendicular to the laser-cut grooves. Raman spectroscopy with an excitation wavelength of 785nm was performed on the epoxy resin facing the cutting surface. The change of Raman spectra was observed at 10 μ m intervals from the laser-cut groove.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Laser cutting of CFRP using the 258 nm laser

Fig. 1 shows a microscope photograph of the cross-section of laser-cut grooves when the stage was moved at speeds of 0.1mm/s and 0.2mm/s. A moving speed of 0.05mm/s achieves separation of the 1.6mm CFRP with a cutting width of 20 μ m which corresponds to the left edge of the CFRP in Fig. 1. This gives an aspect ratio of more than 80. In order to study the characteristics of the high aspect ratio laser cutting, we performed X-ray CT imaging and SEM.

Fig. 1 Cross-section of laser cut grooves

Fig. 2(a) shows the X-ray CT image of CFRP cut by a 258nm laser, (b) shows the CT image of cut by a 1030nm fiber laser, and (c) shows the CT image of cut by a diamond saw. In Fig. 2(b), HAZ is observed with a width of around 200 μ m from the edge. However, in Fig. 2(a), HAZ is less than 5 μ m and the edge shape is the same as Fig. 2(c).

Fig. 3 shows the SEM photograph around the laser cut groove. The edges of carbon fibers are shown by red arrows. In Fig. 3, these edges are covered with a thin layer. In order to understand the nature of the thin layer, we analyzed the components of the thin layer using Raman Spectroscopy.

Fig. 2 X-ray CT image of CFRP
 (a) cut by a 258 nm laser, (b) cut by a 1030 nm fiber laser, (c) cut by a diamond saw

Fig. 3 SEM photograph around the laser cut groove

Fig. 4(a) shows the Raman spectrum of CF, (b) shows the Raman spectrum of epoxy resin far from the groove, and (c) shows the Raman spectrum of the thin layer. Broad D- and G-bands are detected in the CF. Peaks due to ether bonds (C-O-C) at 1150cm^{-1} and carbon-carbon double bonds (C=C) at 1600cm^{-1} are detected in the epoxy resin. The thin layer spectrum (c) is a combination of (a) and (b). Therefore, we conclude that the thin layer is a mixture of CF and epoxy resin.

Fig. 4 Raman spectrum of CFRP

(a) CF, (b) epoxy resin far away from the groove, (c) thin layer

3.2 Thermal damage evaluation

We have also investigated the resin damage induced by laser irradiation. In this study, Raman spectra of the ether bond (C-O-C) and carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) were studied as a function of laser wavelength and distance perpendicular to the surface of the laser-cut groove, to determine the existence and range of damage. Fig. 5(a) shows the Raman spectrum of epoxy resin 200 μm away from the laser-cut groove at a wavelength of 258nm. It is seen that the resin is not affected by the laser irradiation and thermal conduction through the carbon fibers. Fig. 5(b) shows the Raman spectrum at the groove itself. In Fig. 5(a), the peak of the ether bond (C-O-C) and carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) are observed. However, these peaks are not seen in Fig. 5(b), although the signal intensity was two orders of magnitude larger than in Fig. 5(a). From these results, the hypothesis is that these peaks did not appear because the fluorescence increased due to the heating of the epoxy resin even though there was no observable HAZ in the X-ray CT image and the SEM photograph.

Fig. 6 shows the Raman spectra of epoxy resin at a wavelength of 258nm. Two peaks appeared about 50 μm away from the groove, whereas these peaks appeared more than 100 μm away from the groove at wavelengths of 515nm (Fig. 7) and 1030nm (Fig. 8). Fig. 9 shows the absorption coefficient α of graphite and epoxy resin measured by spectroscopic ellipsometry. In Fig. 9(a), the peak of α is around 250nm and in Fig. 9(b), α increases as the wavelength decreases. From these results, it is concluded that both CF and the epoxy resin absorb laser energy at a wavelength of 258nm. However, for the other two wavelengths, only CF absorbs laser energy and the resin is transparent. This leads us to believe that for wavelengths of 515nm and 1030nm, the resin isn't laser-cut directly but is processed by the heat generated at the carbon fibers. However, for 258nm, the cutting process of the resin is a combination of thermal and non-thermal (bond-breaking) processes. For 515nm and 1030nm, the cutting process is predominantly thermal. This explains why the thermal damage area was much smaller for the laser processing at a wavelength of 258nm compared with the other two wavelengths.

Fig. 5 Raman spectrum of epoxy resin

(a) 200 μm from the groove, (b) 0 μm from the groove

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Raman spectrum of epoxy resin at a wavelength of 258nm

(a) 0μm from the groove, (b) 50μm from the groove

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Raman spectrum of epoxy resin at a wavelength of 515nm

(a) 50μm from the groove, (b) 100μm from the groove

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 Raman spectrum of epoxy resin at a wavelength of 1030nm

(a) 50μm from the groove, (b) 110μm from the groove

(a) (b)
 Fig. 9 Absorption coefficient of CFRP components
 (a) graphite, (b) epoxy resin

3.3 Wavelength dependence of removal depth

Fig. 10 shows the wavelength dependence of the removal depth of CFRP laser cutting as a function of irradiated fluence. The removal depth for 258nm is about twice as much compared to 515nm and 1030nm for the same fluence. This result shows that at a wavelength of 258nm, the irradiation energy is more efficiently used for CFRP cutting compared with the other two wavelengths. This result is consistent with the difference in the cutting mechanism described in the previous section. For 258nm, the irradiation energy is more efficiently used because the cutting mechanism is a combination of thermal and direct bond breaking processes.

Fig. 10 Wavelength dependence of removal depth

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the CFRPs were processed at wavelengths of 258nm, 515nm, 1030nm, and Raman spectra of the ether bond (C-O-C) and carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) of the resin was observed as a function of the distance perpendicular to the surface of the laser-cut groove in order to evaluate the existence and range of damage. Based on these results, we summarize the conclusions of this study as follows:

- The thermal damage area for laser cutting at a wavelength of 258nm was 50μm from the

groove, whereas the thermal damage area for wavelengths of 515nm and 1030nm were more than 100 μ m from the groove. It is hypothesized that the 258nm laser irradiation together with thermal process due to the heat generated in carbon fibers, breaks the atomic bond directly.

- The removal depth for the 258nm laser was about twice as much compared to that for the 515nm and 1030nm lasers for the same fluence.

Although we are continuing to investigate the chemical changes in the thermal damage area and the effect on mechanical properties, we have shown in this study that laser cutting using UV lasers has potential as a new technology for CFRP processing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported in part by JST COI Grant Number JPMJCE1313.

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